

ACTUAL PROBLEMS IN TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

R.A. Asanov

Teacher of the Language Teaching Department Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the actual problems of studying the Russian language, describes the difficulties encountered by those wishing to learn this elegant and beautiful language, its phonetic, grammatical and lexical aspects. And also the way to overcome these difficulties and start speaking Russian.*

Keywords: *Russian language, phonetics, orthoepy, phonetic aspect, grammatical aspect, lexical aspect, frequency dictionary.*

Russian is one of the languages, which is difficult to master because of the peculiarities of the Cyrillic alphabet and grammar rules. Also considerable difficulties for the learners of Russian are caused by understanding and application of phraseological expressions in figurative meaning.

Those who want to learn and communicate fluently in Russian don't know where to begin. Currently, many people go to tutoring to learn the Russian language. It's good if you get a good specialist. It may also be that those who want to learn Russian are not taught in a practical way. There are quite a few books that are recommended when learning Russian. So which book to start learning? Which book is better? Also, many people think that in order to start speaking you have to learn the grammar completely. This is not true. Nevertheless, some sections of the language should be noted.

Phonetics and orthoepy are one of the main sections of linguistics and are closely related to grammar and vocabulary. They play an important role in the whole system of the Russian language. Correct pronunciation should be given more importance in the teaching process. "The establishment of correct pronunciation should be dealt with during the entire period of Russian language teaching, since incorrect pronunciation not only hampers students' oral speech, but also affects their orthography"[1].

Correct speech is an important detail in the education of a well-rounded person. A person's vocabulary always helps him to express his thoughts correctly and gives him a broader opportunity to know the reality around him. Sound system play an important role in the acquisition of a second language. Vocabulary and sound culture of the learner is enriched by compliance with the rules of pronunciation of a non-native language. And this factor contributes to the maximum development of outlook and thinking of the learner in a non-native language. "Teaching Russian literary pronunciation is as necessary as teaching, spelling and grammar. The conscious cultivation of literary pronunciation is of great importance for students' mastery of the Russian literary language [2].

Phonetic aspect. Problems for some begin at a very early stage when they start learning the alphabet. At this stage there are difficulties with the pronunciation of letters, as well as understanding the features of -Ъ, -Ь signs: they have no sound, these signs separate or indicate the hardness or softness of the preceding consonant letter. Phonetics in the beginning of training can seem difficult for foreigners, so you need to study it carefully and regularly conduct phonetic exercises, phonetic dictations, to practice the sounds. It is necessary to learn to distinguish sounds

by ear, because there are certain difficulties in recognition of a word by its sound (for example, the words "gas" and "glas" sound the same to foreigners).

The grammatical aspect. Russian is a flexive language, that is, in the expression of grammatical meanings word change with the help of inflections dominates. In this aspect special attention should be paid to inflection, i.e. change of a word by grammatical categories of gender, number and case. Special difficulties are caused by the system of cases of the Russian language. Also a great difficulty in the study of Russian is syntax for foreigners, namely the word order. In a sentence there is no strictly fixed place for this or that member. This order of words is called free or not fixed. Consequently, words can go in various sequences. However, the arrangement of words in a sentence depends on the purpose of the statement, its communicative task [3]. The sentences composed by you, should be correct and fully reflect the communicative purposes: to be able to fully convey your thoughts and feelings, and at the same time not to change the meaning and logic of what is said.

Lexical aspect. When studying the vocabulary of the Russian language, many have difficulty interpreting the meaning of a word. After all, in Russian one word can have several meanings, for example pen: the pen with which we write, the pen of a child, the door handle.

If you pay attention to the language we use, what percentage of the language do we use? To master Russian, to be able to communicate properly, it is necessary to know pronouns, verb conjugation, verb tenses, gender and cases. Every day we use a limited number of words, we use the same words. You should also learn words from frequent dictionaries. There are different frequency dictionaries: frequency dictionary of nouns, frequency dictionary of adjectives, frequency dictionary of verbs, etc.

Be sure to read books in the language you study. And it is better to take such books, where the text you understand at least 50%. For example, you read short stories and you saw an unfamiliar word, underline it with a pencil, do not immediately go to the dictionary to find its translation, finish for example, 1 chapter, then go back to the underlined words. Look up the translation of a word, make sure you write it down and make a sentence with it. You must learn how to use these words in sentences. When you learn words in the same way, make up sentences with these words, so you will remember them faster.

Apart from that you need communication. Friends who are also learning the language with you will help you to communicate. If you do not have such people near you, do not worry, in the world are a lot of people who learn it as you and they also need to practice the language. You can communicate with them through apps, there are many, for example: Tandem, HiNative, Polyglot Club, HelloTalk, Conversation, Exchange, InterPals, Speaky, The Mixxer

And remember something else, you'll never fully master a language if you don't know the culture of the language you're learning. When you learn a language, you're not only learning the language itself, but also its culture. Learning languages is so much fun and interesting, try and experience it for yourself!!!

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